

An analysis of the number groups within the Collatz Conjecture

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Abstract. Number Groups are systems of numbers that arise when a mathematical operation is applied to all numbers based on their parity. For example, Collatz's Conjecture states for all even numbers divide them by 2, and for all odd numbers, multiply them by three and add 1. As a result of this, order arises in a field due to the restrictions that are applied; therefore, if given an arbitrary number, it is possible to analyze all groups that the number is an element of and determine the sequence of the given element as it approaches the value of whatever the arithmetical restrictions tend towards

1. INTRODUCTION AND MAIN RESULTS

(1.1) Given some arbitrary Natural number n , apply the following restrictions presented by Lothar Collatz. Which will be called the Collatz space.

$$1.1.1 \quad f(n) = \begin{cases} \frac{n}{2} & \text{if } n \equiv 0 \pmod{2}, \\ \frac{3n+1}{2} & \text{if } n \equiv 1 \pmod{2}. \end{cases}$$

When performing this operation repeatedly to form a sequence, five Sets of numbers (Groups) and two colors of numbers, Red and Green, emerge. Each group has its own respective operations that will occur based on a numbers Color and Group Configuration. With the last digit of the number acting as a designator for the

number in its respective group.

Color[Parity|Group and the last digit of the number],

For example, the following forms exist for these numbers

$$1 = R[\text{even}| B1], 315 = G[\text{odd}| A5], 7854 = R[\text{odd}| E4]$$

Every number has a color and group configuration.

(1.2) Determining a Number's Color

The following algorithm will generate each set of colors in the collatz space given.

Let n be a natural number. The color of n is determined by the following, by formulae and will be important for arbitration.

$$1.2.1 \text{ Green}_n = 4 \left\lfloor \frac{n_i}{2} \right\rfloor + 2 + (n_i \bmod 2)$$

$$1.2.2 \text{ Red}_n = 4 \left\lfloor \frac{n_i}{2} \right\rfloor + (n_i \bmod 2)$$

n_i in 1.2.1 and 1.2.2 is the indexed of the number in its respective color set with.

$i \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ including 0, For example, if given $n_{22} = 23$, $\text{Green}_n = 47$ then $\text{Red}_n = 45$

respectfully. To determine the color of a number in collatz space given some arbitrary Natural number, n use the following function.

$$1.2.3 \text{ Color}(n) = \begin{cases} \text{Red} & \text{if } n \bmod 4 = 0 \text{ or } n \bmod 4 = 1 \\ \text{Green} & \text{if } n \bmod 4 = 2 \text{ or } n \bmod 4 = 3 \end{cases}$$

Let n be a natural number; the color and parity of n are determined as follows.

Function 1.2.3 takes a number and outputs its color and parity, if a number modulo 4 = {0,1}, then it is in the Red color group (R), with Color(n) = {0} being even and Color(n) = {1} being odd,

for example $Color(56) = R[0] = R\{even\}$.

Similarly, if a number modulo 4 = {2,3}, then it is in the Green color group (G), with Color(n) = {2} being even and Color(n) = {3} being odd, for example

$Color(171) = G[3] = G\{odd\}$

(1.3) Determining a Number's group.

1.3.1 Every number belongs to one and only one of the five groups in a collatz space (A, B, C, D, and E). Each group has a set of transformations and operations that differ based on the number's color and parity.

Group A is unique and will be saved at the end of the list,

Group B uses the following sets of transformations.

1. $R[even|B1] \rightarrow R[even|E4]$, 2. $R[even|B6] \rightarrow R[even|D3]$
3. $R[odd|B1] \rightarrow R[odd|E4]$ 4. $R[odd|B6] \rightarrow R[even|D8]$
5. $G[even|B1] \rightarrow G[even|E4]$, 6. $G[even|B6] \rightarrow R[odd|D3]$
7. $G[odd|B1] \rightarrow R[odd|E4]$ 8. $G[odd|B6] \rightarrow R[odd|D8]$

Group C uses the following sets of transformations.

1. $R[even|C2] \rightarrow R[even|B1]$, 2. $R[even|C7] \rightarrow G[even|C2]$
3. $R[odd|C2] \rightarrow R[even|B6]$ 4. $R[odd|C7] \rightarrow R[odd|C2]$
5. $G[even|C2] \rightarrow R[odd|B1]$, 6. $G[even|C7] \rightarrow R[even|C2]$
7. $G[odd|C2] \rightarrow R[odd|B6]$ 8. $G[odd|C7] \rightarrow G[odd|C2]$

Group D uses the following sets of transformations, each of which flips color every 100th indexed Color Group for transformations to A.

1. $R[even|D3] \rightarrow R[odd|A0]^{oQ}$, 2. $R[even|D8] \rightarrow R[even|E4]$
3. $R[odd|D3] \rightarrow R[even|A0]^{oo}$ 4. $R[odd|D8] \rightarrow R[even|E9]$
5. $G[even|D3] \rightarrow G[odd|A0]^{oQ}$, 6. $G[even|D8] \rightarrow R[odd|E4]$
7. $G[odd|D3] \rightarrow G[even|A0]^{oo}$ 8. $G[odd|D8] \rightarrow R[odd|E9]$

Group E uses the following sets of transformations.

1. $R[even|E4] \rightarrow R[even|C2]$, 2. $R[even|E9] \rightarrow G[even|D8]$
3. $R[odd|E4] \rightarrow R[even|C7]$ 4. $R[odd|E9] \rightarrow R[odd|D8]$
5. $G[even|E4] \rightarrow R[odd|C2]$, 6. $G[even|E9] \rightarrow R[even|D8]$
7. $G[odd|E4] \rightarrow R[odd|C7]$ 8. $G[odd|E9] \rightarrow G[odd|D8]$

Group A Transformations and rules,

For all elements in Group A they will have the following parities.

left = *Qo* : A Left parity number will always end in the number 5, and once the collatz mathematical operation is performed will generate a number that belongs in Group B

right = *oQ* : A Right parity number is always an even number that leads with an odd digit for example, 10, 30, 50, and 70 are right parity, and once the collatz mathematical operation is performed, will generate a left number less than it in Group A

Perfect = *oo* : is a number the collatz mathematical operation is performed will yield another number less than it in Group A. Every perfect number sequence will end in a number that has right parity.

right = *oQ* , *left* = *Qo* , and *perfect* = *oo*

To determine the group that a number is an element of, take its final digit. And place it in the group with the same digit identities.

Group A is made of all numbers ending in {0 or 5}.

For example $315 = G[odd|A5] = G[odd|A]$

Group B is made of all numbers ending in {1 or 6}.

For example $316 = G[\text{odd}|B6] = G[\text{odd}|B]$

Group C is made of all numbers ending in {2 or 7}.

For example $317 = G[\text{odd}|C7] = G[\text{odd}|C]$

Group D is made of all numbers ending in {3 or 8}.

For example $318 = G[\text{odd}|D8] = G[\text{odd}|D]$

Group E is made of all numbers ending in {4 or 9}.

For example $319 = G[\text{odd}|E9] = G[\text{odd}|E]$

And if given the notation for some arbitrary number in its respective group then it follows that the number will end with either of the two numbers of its group

identity; for example, if given some number, $G[\text{odd}|A]$ then it follows that

$G[\text{odd}|A] = G[\text{odd}|A0]$ or $G[\text{odd}|A5]$ with the number leading digits being a green number ending in 0 or 5, ie(2230, 2150, 2235, 2155,...) are all green numbers in the $G[\text{odd}|A]$ notation.

All numbers have a direction up, down, left, or right. And the direction sequence will change based on a numbers colors group.

Red Group:

Up Number formula: $8n_1 - 8$, Always Even $n \bmod 8 = 0$ ending in either 0, 8, 6, 4, 2.

Down Number formula: $8n_1 - 7$, Always Odd $n \bmod 8 = 1$ ending in either 1, 9, 7, 5, 3.

Left Number formula: $8n_1 - 4$, Always Even $n \bmod 8 = 4$ ending in either 4, 2, 0, 8, 6.

Right Number formula: $8n_1 - 3$, Always Odd $n \bmod 8 = 5$ ending in either 5, 3, 1, 9, 7.

Green Group:

Up Number formula: $8n_1 - 6$, Always Even $n \bmod 8 = 2$ ending in either 2, 0, 8, 6, 4.

Down Number formula: $8n_1 - 5$, Always Odd $n \bmod 8 = 3$ ending in either 3, 1, 9, 7, 5.

Left Number formula: $8n_1 - 2$, Always Even $n \bmod 8 = 6$ ending in either 6, 4, 2, 0, 8.

Right Number formula: $8n_1 - 1$, Always Odd $n \bmod 8 = 7$ ending in either 7, 5, 3, 1, 9.

2.1 Generation of sequences in collatz space using a universal index $n_i, i \in \mathbb{Z}^+$

Unique sequences can be used to generate the elements of all groups based on using the universal index as the input. Respectfully for each group.

2.1.1: Universal Sequence Formulae

The formula; $a_n = 5(n + 1) - 5$, will generate a sequence of $a_n \in A$ with the number ending in 0 if n is even and 5 if n is odd.

The formula; $b_n = 5(n + 1) - 4$, will generate a sequence of $b_n \in B$ with the number ending in 1 if n is even and 6 if n is odd.

The formula; $c_n = 5(n + 1) - 3$, will generate a sequence of $c_n \in C$ with the number ending in 2 if n is even and 7 if n is odd.

The formula; $d_n = 5(n + 1) - 2$, will generate a sequence of $d_n \in D$ with the number ending in 3 if n is even and 8 if n is odd.

The formula; $e_n = 5(n + 1) - 1$, will generate a sequence of $e_n \in E$ with the number ending in 4 if n is even and 9 if n is odd.

Conversely, these sequences, if given some integer n, will return a number adhering to the numeric restrictions of the given group. For example, let's say we are given $n = 0$, and then when n is inputted into the formulae in 2.1.1, the output will be $a_n = 0, b_n = 1, c_n = 2, d_n = 3$, and $e_n = 4$.

The following formulae will be used to determine the universal index of a given number within its respective group.

The formula; $n_i = \frac{a_n + 5}{5} - 1$, where a_n an integer ending in 0 or 5 within set A.

The formula; $n_i = \frac{b_n + 4}{5} - 1$, where b_n an integer ending in 1 or 6 within set B.

The formula; $n_i = \frac{c_n + 3}{5} - 1$, where c_n an integer ending in 2 or 7 within set C.

The formula; $n_i = \frac{d_n + 2}{5} - 1$, where d_n an integer ending in 3 or 8 within set D.

The formula; $n_i = \frac{e_n + 1}{5} - 1$, where e_n an integer ending in 4 or 9 within set E.

For example, let's say we are given $a_n = 10, b_n = 11, c_n = 12, d_n = 13$, and $e_n = 14$, and. When n is inputted into the formulae in 2.1.1, the output will represent $n = 0$, thus showing us that the given numbers are within the same universal identifier.

2.2 Generation of sequences using the universal index.

While observing the universal operations on all odd and even numbers, more operations emerge based on parity within the given group.

It is important to note that notation $n_{group|parity}$, where the group designates the operation to be performed, and parity represents whether the given n is odd or even, This process will be necessary to determine what operation affects the universal identifier.

Group operations are based on the universal index parity.

$$A_{group} = \begin{cases} n_{a|even} \rightarrow \frac{n_a}{2} & = n_a \text{ even or odd} \\ n_{a|odd} \rightarrow 3 \cdot n_{a \rightarrow b} & = n_b \text{ odd} \end{cases}$$

$$B_{group} = \begin{cases} n_{b|even} \rightarrow 3 \cdot n_{b \rightarrow e} & = n_e \text{ even or odd} \\ n_{b|odd} \rightarrow \frac{n_{b \rightarrow d} - 1}{2} & = n_d \text{ odd or even} \end{cases}$$

$$C_{group} = \begin{cases} n_{c|even} \rightarrow \frac{n_{c \rightarrow b}}{2} & = n_b \text{ even or odd} \\ n_{c|odd} \rightarrow 3n_c + 1 & = n_c \text{ even} \end{cases}$$

$$D_{group} = \begin{cases} n_{d|even} \rightarrow 3n_{d \rightarrow a} + 1 & = n_e \text{ even or odd} \\ n_{d|odd} \rightarrow \frac{n_{d \rightarrow e} - 1}{2} & = n_e \text{ odd or even} \end{cases}$$

$$E_{group} = \begin{cases} n_{e|even} \rightarrow \frac{n_{e \rightarrow c}}{2} & = n_c \text{ even or odd} \\ n_{e|odd} \rightarrow 3n_{e \rightarrow d} + 2 & = n_d \text{ odd} \end{cases}$$

The following expressions can be used to determine the following number in the Collatz sequence based on the universal index of some integer n_{group} . When utilizing this approach with integers greater than 0, two loops emerge. The first is the 4, 2, 1 loop, or in group notation, the B0, C0, E0 loop. The second is the 0 loop, or in group notation, the A0 Loop.

3.0 Proof of Groups used in analysis.

Color and Parity Analysis:

3.1.0 When referencing n_i as an element of the positive integers.

3.1.1 Red n_{i+1} Transforms.

- Each number n_i in the cycle has a color (Red or Green), direction (Up, Down, Left or Right), and Parity(Even or odd).
- If n_i is even up and Red: n_{i+1} will be odd, it remains in the Red group and changes directionality to down.
- If n_i is even left and Red: n_{i+1} will be odd, it remains in the Red group and changes directionality to right.
- If n_i is odd down and Red: n_{i+1} will be even, it moves into the Green group and changes directionality to up.
- If n_i is odd right and Red: n_{i+1} will be even, it moves into the Green group and changes directionality to left.

3.1.2 Green n_{i+1} Transforms.

- If n_i is even up and Green: n_{i+1} will be odd, it remains in the Green group. and changes directionality to down.
- If n_i is even left and Green: n_{i+1} will be odd, it remains in the Green group and changes directionality to right.
- If n_i is odd down and Green: n_{i+1} will be even, it moves to the Red group and changes directionality to left.
- If n_i is odd right and Green: n_{i+1} will be even, it moves to the Red group and changes directionality to up.

3.2 For group-dependent directional change independent of Color.

When referencing n_i as an element of the universal index, when the index is applied to the respective formulae in 2.1.1, the resulting number will have a specific

3.2.1 direction, color, and parity as follows:

- If n_i is even, up, and Red: n_{i+1} will be odd, Red, and right.
- If n_i is odd, down, and Red: n_{i+1} will be even, Green, and left.
- If n_i is even, up, and Green: n_{i+1} will be odd, Green, and right.
- If n_i is odd, down, and Green: n_{i+1} will be even, Red, and up.
- If n_i is even, left, and Red: n_{i+1} will be odd, Red, and down.
- If n_i is odd, right, and Red: n_{i+1} will be even, Green, and up.
- If n_i is even, left, and Green: n_{i+1} will be odd, Green, and down.
- If n_i is odd, right, and Green: n_{i+1} will be even, Red, and left.

3.3.1 **Theorem 1.0:** Each and every number belongs to one and only one group.

1. Group Definitions:

> Group A: Numbers ending in 0 or 5.

> Group B: Numbers ending in 1 or 6.

> Group C: Numbers ending in 2 or 7.

> Group D: Numbers ending in 3 or 8.

> Group E: Numbers ending in 4 or 9.

2. Let be some arbitrary $n \in \mathbb{N}$. The last digit of n is one of $\{0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9\}$.

3. Assignment to a Group:

> Based on the last digit n , assign n to the applicable group:

-if the last digit is 0 or 5, n is in Group A.

-if the last digit is 1 or 6, n is in Group B.

-if the last digit is 2 or 7, n is in Group C.

-if the last digit is 3 or 8, n is in Group D.

-if the last digit is 4 or 9, n is in Group E.

4. Uniqueness: Each number ends in exactly one digit, and, therefore can belong to one and only one group.

Lemma 1.0: Each and every number belongs to one and only one color group, Red or Green, based on its properties.

1. Red Assignment: if $n \bmod 4 \in \{0, 1\}$, Then n is Red.

2. Green Assignment: if $n \bmod 4 \in \{2, 3\}$, Then n is Green.

3. Uniqueness: No Integer or Natural can satisfy both conditions simultaneously.

Red Assignment proof:

1. For any n_i , Calculate $n_i \bmod 4$, if the result is 0 or 1, n_i is assigned to the red color group.

Green Assignment proof:

2. For any n_i , Calculate $n_i \bmod 4$, if the result is 2 or 3, n_i is assigned to the Green color group.

Since $n_i \bmod 4$ can only yield one of the four possible elements: 0, 1, 2, or 3 based on modulo 4 properties. It follows that a number can only be classified as either red or green, but not both. This completes the lemma.

Theorem 1.1: Directionalization

Each and every number has a unique direction (up, Down, Left, Right) based on its properties.

Definitions:

1. A Up number is defined as $n_i \bmod 8 \in \{0, 2\}$.
2. A Down number is defined as $n_i \bmod 8 \in \{1, 3\}$.
3. A Left number is defined as $n_i \bmod 8 \in \{4, 6\}$.
4. A Right number is defined as $n_i \bmod 8 \in \{5, 7\}$.

Up Assignment proof:

>For any n_i , Calculate $n_i \bmod 8$, if the result is 0 or 2, n_i is assigned to the up color group.

Down Assignment proof:

>For any n_i , Calculate $n_i \bmod 8$, if the result is 1 or 3, n_i is assigned to the down color group.

Left Assignment proof:

>For any n_i , Calculate $n_i \bmod 8$, if the result is 4 or 6, n_i is assigned to the left color group.

Right Assignment proof:

>For any n_i , Calculate $n_i \bmod 8$, if the result is 5 or 7, n_i is assigned to the right color group.

Since $n_i \bmod 8$ can only yield one of the four possible elements: 0, 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7 based on modulo 8 properties. It follows that a number can only be classified with one direction.

lemma 1.2: Whenever using the universal index, $n_{i+1} = n_i + 1$, the number, when not in universal index notation calculated by the Universal sequence formula, will change by 5.

1. Let n_i be a number in the universal index. When we increment by one we get

$$n_i + 1 = n_{i+1}$$

2. Now when calculating the universal index by the universal sequence formula

$$Group_n = 5n + c, \text{ where } c \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}:$$

> if the group is A , $c = 0$

> if the group is B , $c = 1$

> if the group is C , $c = 2$

> if the group is D , $c = 3$

> if the group is E , $c = 4$

3. Since the universal index will be multiplied by 5, and added by some constant based on the group, it follows that n_{i+1} will be some multiple of 5 $\implies$ When given some arbitrary index in its respective group, n_{i+1} will be 5 more than the previous. This completes the lemma.

Lemma 1.3: Each Transformation rule preserves group structure.

Let n_i be some number in Group A, B, C, D, or E. with each group is defined by its last digit number:

-if the last digit is 0 or 5, n is in Group A.

-if the last digit is 1 or 6, n is in Group B.

-if the last digit is 2 or 7, n is in Group C.

-if the last digit is 3 or 8, n is in Group D.

-if the last digit is 4 or 9, n is in Group E.

Transformation of group A by universal index:

1. If $n_i \in A$ and is even then: $\frac{n_i}{2} = n_{i/2} \in A$ with $n_{i/2} < n_i$, since Group A is only composed of numbers ending in 5 or 0, it follows that the only even indexed numbers in A end in 0 $\implies$ any numbers ending in 0, when divided by 2 and, will

either yield a number ending in 0 or a 5. Thus if $n_i \in A$ and even, then $\frac{n_i}{2}$ will remain in group A.

2. If $n_i \in A$ and is odd then: $3 \cdot n_i = n_{3i} \in B$ with $n_i < n_{3i}$, since Group A is only composed of numbers ending in 5 or 0, it follows that the only odd indexed numbers in A end in 5 $\Rightarrow$ any numbers ending in 5, when its universal index in A is multiplied 3 will always yield a number ending in 6. Thus if $n_i \in A$ and odd, then $3 \cdot n_i$ will move to group B.

> For example, $n_i \in A = 1$, then $3 \cdot n_i = n_{3i}$, $n_{i \in B} = 3$,

> Then, using the Universal sequence formula, $n_{i \in B} = 3$, will be $5n_i + 1 = 16$,

> Since 16 ends in a 6, it gets assigned to group B. and will always be Even.

Transformation of group B by universal index:

3. If $n_i \in B$ and is even then: $3 \cdot n_i = n_{3i} \in E$ with $n_i < n_{3i}$, since Group B is only composed of numbers ending in 1 or 6, it follows that the only even indexed numbers will B end in 1 $\Rightarrow$ any numbers ending in 1, when its universal index in A is multiplied by 3 will always yield a number ending in 4. Thus if $n_i \in B$ and even, then $3 \cdot n_i = n_{3i} \in E$ will move to group E.

> For example, $n_i \in B = 2$, then $3 \cdot n_i = n_{3i}$, $n_{i \in E} = 6$,

> Then, using the Universal sequence formula, $n_{i \in E} = 6$, will be $5n_i + 4 = 34$,

> Since 34 ends in a 4, it gets assigned to group E and will always be Even.

4. If $n_i \in B$ is odd then: $\frac{n_i - 1}{2} = n_{i \in D}$ with $n_{i \in D} < n_{i \in B}$, then since Group B is only composed of numbers ending in 1 or 6, it follows that the only odd indexed numbers

in B end in 6 $\Rightarrow$ any numbers ending in 6, when its universal index in B is subtracted by 1 and divided by 2 will yield a number ending in 6. Thus if $n_i \in B$ and odd, then its transformation will move to group D.

> For example, $n_i \in B = 3$, then $\frac{n_i - 1}{2} = n_{3i'}$, $n_{i \in D} = 1$,

> Then, using the Universal sequence formula, $n_{i \in D} = 1$, will be $5n_i + 3 = 8$,

> Since 8 ends in an 8, it gets assigned to group D. The numbers produced by this group's universal formula will always end in 8 or 3 and thus will be assigned to D.

Transformation of group C by universal index:

5. If $n_i \in C$ and is even then: $\frac{n_c}{2} = n_c \in B$ with $n_{i \in B} < n_{i \in C}$, since Group C is only composed of numbers ending in 2 or 7, it follows that the only even indexed numbers in C end in 2 $\Rightarrow$ any numbers ending in 2, when its universal index in C is divided by 2 will yield a number ending in 1 or 6. Thus if $n_i \in C$ and even, then $\frac{n_c}{2} = n_c \in B$ thus will move to group B.

> For example, $n_i \in C = 2$, then $\frac{n_c}{2} = n_b$, $n_{i \in B} = 1$,

> Then, using the Universal sequence formula, $n_{i \in B} = 1$, will be $5n_i + 1 = 6$,

> Since 6 ends in a 6, it gets assigned to group B. The numbers produced by this group's universal formula will always end in 1 or 6 and thus will be assigned to B.

6. If $n_i \in C$ and is odd then: $3n_i + 1 = n_c \in C_{\text{even}}$ with $n_{i \in C} < n_{i \text{ new} \in C}$, since Group C is only composed of numbers ending in 2 or 7, it follows that the only odd indexed numbers in C end in 7 $\Rightarrow$ any numbers ending in 7, when its universal index in

C is multiplied by 3 and added 1 will yield always yield a number ending in 2.

Thus if $n_i \in C$ and odd, then $3n_i + 1 = n_c \in C_{even}$ thus will remain in group C.

> For example, $n_i \in C = 5$, then $3n_i + 1 = n_c \in C_{even}$, $n_{i \in C} = 16$,

> Then, using the Universal sequence formula, $n_{i \in C} = 16$, will be $5n_i + 2 = 82$,

> Since 82 ends in a 2, it gets assigned to group B. The numbers produced by this group's universal formula will always end in 2 and thus will be assigned to C.

Transformation of group D by universal index:

7. If $n_i \in D$ and is even then: $3n_i + 2 = n_D \in A$ with $n_{i \in D} < n_{i \in A}$, since Group D is only composed of numbers ending in 3 or 8, it follows that the only even indexed numbers in D end in 3 $\Rightarrow$ any numbers ending in 3, when its universal index in D is multiplied by 3 and incremented by 2 will yield a number ending in 0.

Thus if $n_i \in D$ and even, then $3n_i + 2 = n_D \in A$ thus will move to group A.

> For example, $n_i \in D = 2$, then $3n_i + 2 = n_D$, $n_{i \in D} = 8$,

> Then, using the Universal sequence formula, $n_{i \in D} = 8$, will be $5n_i + 0 = 40$,

> Since 40 ends in a 0, it gets assigned to group A. The numbers produced by this group's universal formula will always end in 0 and thus will be assigned to A.

8. If $n_i \in D$ and is odd then: $\frac{n_{iD}-1}{2} = n_D \in E$ with $n_{i \in E} < n_{i_{new} \in D}$, since Group D is only composed of numbers ending in 2 or 7, it follows that the only odd indexed numbers in D end in 7 $\Rightarrow$ any numbers ending in 7, when its universal index in D is subtracted by 1 and divided by 2 it will yield a number ending in 3 or 8. Thus

if $n_i \in D$ and odd, then $\frac{n_{iD}-1}{2} = n_D \in E$ thus will move to group E.

> For example, $n_i \in D = 3$, then $\frac{n_{iD}-1}{2} = n_D \in E$, $n_{i \in E} = 1$,

> Then, using the Universal sequence formula, $n_{i \in E} = 1$, will be $5n_i + 4 = 4$,

> Since 4 ends in a 4, it gets assigned to Group E. The numbers produced by this group's universal formula will always end in 4 or 9 and thus will be assigned to E.

Transformation of group E by universal index:

9. If $n_i \in E$ and is even then: $\frac{n_E}{2} = n_E \in C$ with $n_{i \in C} < n_{i \in E}$, since Group E is only composed of numbers ending in 4 or 9, it follows that the only even indexed numbers in E end in 4 $\Rightarrow$ any numbers ending in 4, when its universal index in E is divided by 2 will yield a number ending in 2 or 7. Thus if $n_i \in E$ and even, then $\frac{n_E}{2} = n_E \in C$ thus will move to group C.

> For example, $n_i \in E = 22$, then $\frac{n_E}{2} = n_E$, $n_{i \in C} = 11$,

> Then, using the Universal sequence formula, $n_{i \in C} = 11$, will be $5n_i + 2 =$

57,

> Since 57 ends in a 7, it gets assigned to group C. The numbers produced by this group's universal formula will always end in 2 or 7 and thus will be assigned to C.

10. If $n_i \in E$ and is odd then: $3n + 2 = n_E \in D$ with $n_{i \in E} < n_{i \in D}$, since Group E is only composed of numbers ending in 4 or 9, it follows that the only odd indexed numbers in D end in 9 $\Rightarrow$ any numbers ending in 9, when its universal index in D is multiplied by 3 and incremented by 2 it will yield a number ending in 3 or 8. Thus if $n_i \in E$ and odd, then $3n + 2 = n_E \in D$ thus will move to group D.

> For example, $n_i \in E = 3$, then $3n + 2 = n_E \in D$, $n_{i \in D} = 11$,

>Then, using the Universal sequence formula, $n_{i \in D} = 11$, will be $5n_i + 3 = 58$,

> Since 58 ends in an 8, it gets assigned to Group D. The numbers produced by this group's universal formula will always end in 8 and thus will be assigned to D.

Conclusion: Since each transformation obeys and preserves group structure, and the transformed number will always fall in one of the groups, we can conclude the lemma holds true.

Theorem 1.2: For any number n_i in the universal index, applying all of the rules of transformation will eventually lead to a known cycle.

1. Start with any number n_0 in the universal index, by definition theorem 1.0, let it belong to one of the groups: A, B, C, D, or E.
2. By lemma 1.3, each rule of transformation preserves the structure of a group. Therefore, as a result, n_1 , the next number in the sequence must belong to a group based on the transformation n_0 .

>For example if n_0 is in group A and is even, the transformation,

$n_1 = \frac{n_0}{2}$ which will keep n_1 in group A.

> If n_0 is in group A and is odd, $n_1 = 3n_0$ and this transformation will move n_1 to group B.

The structure of groups ensures that the transformations are consistent and predictable allowing us to track the behaviour of the sequence.

3. As the sequence progresses, the transformation rules either reduce the magnitude of the number, or shift it between groups in a predictable way.

And given that any groups structure is preserved and each group has a finite set of possible digital endings (0-9), the sequence will be bound to revisit some of the same groups, and therefore leading to a predictable cycle.

4. All transformations defined by the Universal index and its applicable groups structure inherently will guide the sequence towards known cycles, such as the 4-2-1; because of this a sequence will either decrease or stabilize into a repetitive pattern.
5. In conclusion: By consistent application of the transformation rules ie lemma 1.3, the sequence must terminate in a known cycle. Thus, for any given number k and $k+1$, the rules will hold according to their respective group.

Corollary 1.0: Convergence of even numbers in group A.

For any arbitrary even number n in Group A, the sequence will always terminate in an odd number ending in 5.

1. Let n_0 be an even number in Group A. By definition, it will end in 0.
2. If n_0 is even, the transformation $n_{i+1} = n_i/2$ will be applied. Ad nauseam, until n_i becomes an odd number, still within group A.
3. The first odd number reached in the sequence in Group A must end in 5, as Group A consists of numbers ending in 0 or 5.

Conclusion: Any even number in Group A will eventually terminate in an odd number ending in 5, ensuring the sequence will follow group structure; it will transform to B.

Corollary 1.1: When incrementing the given Universal index of a group by +1, Directionality and color change predictably.

Definition: Colors and groups form the following sequence, $T = \{(R|Up), (R|Down), (G|Up), (G|Down), (R|Left), (R|Right), (G|Left), (G|Right)\}$.

1. Let n_i be a number within the universal index. By definition, to determine the number in each group based on the index, apply the Universal Index Formula.

$$Group_n = 5n + c, \text{ where } c \in \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}:$$

> if the group is *A*, $c = 0$

> if the group is *B*, $c = 1$

> if the group is *C*, $c = 2$

> if the group is *D*, $c = 3$

> if the group is *E*, $c = 4$

> For example if $n_i = 1$, then

> if the group is *A*, $5(1) + 0$

> if the group is *B*, $5(1) + 1$

> if the group is *C*, $5(1) + 2$

> if the group is *D*, $5(1) + 3$

> if the group is *E*, $5(1) + 4$

2. When $n_i + 1 = n_{i+1}$ A numbers, directionality can be found by incrementing in the given sequence T by 5 elements.

3. Let's take $n_i = 10$ in Group A (where $c = 0$), Which is Green and up

$T_3 = (G|Up)$ when placed within the color and directionality formulae. In

addition, according to the Universal index Formula:

$$Group_n = 5n + c = 5(2) + 0 = 10$$

Incrementing by $n_i + 1 = n_{i+1} = 15$, When following the Sequence T_n, n_{i+1}

will move 5 elements ahead $T_{n+5} = T_{3+5} = (G|Right)$, in Group A, This

process can be performed for every universal index number and, once placed

in the directionality function, will shift the directionality by 5.

Theorem 1.3: every possible sequence of transformations starting from any positive integer given its directionality, color, and group inevitably leads to the cycle involving 1.

1. Let n_0 be an even number in some arbitrary group, directionality, or color. By definition n_{0+1} will be in a predicted group.
2. For example, let's say if given $Group_n = k$ for some number with a specific directionality, color, and group properties, then $Group_{n+1} = k + 1$ will naturally follow the transformation rules and move to its new position in the applicable group and in another sequence. Since this number will be subject to the rules of transformation, will lead to 1.

4.0 Conclusion:

By applying group and color analysis, each transformation within Collatz space will reduce the magnitude of the initial and final value of a sequence except in the special case of the value of $n_0 = n_k = 1$.

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